

**From Meaningful Human Control
to Appropriate Human Judgement:
Tracking the Normative Erosion of Human Oversight
in the UN LAWS Debate (2017–2025)**

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Abstract. The Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW) Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) has debated Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (LAWS) for over a decade without producing a binding instrument. The most recent negotiating text—the Revised Rolling Text of 2025—introduces the formula “appropriate human judgement and control” in place of the earlier concept of “meaningful human control” (MHC). This paper argues that this terminological substitution is not a neutral convergence but a substantive normative shift, one that progressively hollows out the human oversight requirement that international humanitarian law (IHL) compliance demands. Drawing on an original corpus analysis of over 300 United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs (UNODA) and Reaching Critical Will (RCW) documents spanning 2017–2025, supplemented by a supervised stance classifier (ban/regulate/cautious) and close reading of state positions, the paper traces three phases in the GGE debate and identifies a structural misalignment: quantitative evidence shows that formal documents converge on regulatory language while advocacy corpora continue to register strong prohibitionist demands. The paper further analyses the strategic motivations underlying the positions of key state actors—the United States, United Kingdom, Russia, Israel, France, Germany, Austria, and Italy—and argues that the terminological shift towards “human judgement” reflects a diplomatic accommodation of the cautious bloc at the cost of a standard that can be satisfied by systems operating without human involvement at the moment of engagement. The implications for IHL compliance and for any future governance instrument are assessed.

Keywords: lethal autonomous weapons systems; meaningful human control; human judgement; CCW/GGE; international humanitarian law; text mining; accountability gap; arms control

1 Introduction

On 1 June 2025, approximately 150 commercial first-person-view (FPV) drones struck four Russian strategic aviation bases, damaging Tu-95MS, Tu-22M3, and Tu-160 bombers across four different regions of Russian territory simultaneously. The drones had been assembled from consumer-grade components and guided by AI targeting algorithms trained on open-source aviation imagery. The operation did not overwhelm Russian air defences: it bypassed them entirely, because those defences had been designed for threats arriving from outside the territory—not from civilian logistics flows already moving within it.¹ The question of whether such systems fall within or outside the international legal frameworks governing autonomous weapons is not academic. It is operationally consequential—and the answer that the CCW/GGE process is producing, after more than a decade of negotiations, may be the wrong one.

The CCW Group of Governmental Experts on LAWS has been working since 2014 to produce a regulatory framework for autonomous weapons. After more than a decade of deliberation, the 2025 Revised Rolling Text represents the most complete normative output to date. Yet a close reading of that document, set against the evolution of negotiating language over the period 2017–2025, reveals a significant conceptual shift: the formula “meaningful human control” (MHC), which had anchored the debate since its introduction by civil society actors in 2013–2014, has been progressively displaced by the weaker formulation “appropriate human judgement and control”. The 2025 Rolling Text institutionalises this substitution.

This paper asks: what does this terminological shift mean for the substance of the oversight requirement? Is it a pragmatic convergence that makes a future instrument more politically achievable, or a normative erosion that accommodates systems capable of selecting and engaging targets without human involvement at the moment of the decision? The argument advanced here is that it is the latter—and that this can be demonstrated both through the textual record of the negotiations and through a systematic analysis of the strategic motivations that drove the key state actors.

The paper makes two contributions. First, it provides an original quantitative analysis of over 300 UNODA and RCW documents spanning 2017–2025, tracking the frequency of key terms and the distribution of negotiating positions using a supervised stance classifier. This produces an empirical map of how the debate evolved, and confirms that the convergence visible in formal GGE documents conceals persistent divergence in the wider negotiating community. Second, it offers a systematic analysis of state positions

¹Singh, A. (2025). ‘Spider Web: Far-Reaching Implications for the Future of Warfare’. *USI of India Journal*, 155(641); Bondar, K. (2025). *How Ukraine’s Operation ‘Spider’s Web’ Redefines Asymmetric Warfare*. Washington DC: CSIS, 2 June.

and the strategic logics underlying them—moving beyond the standard tripartite typology (ban/regulate/cautious) to identify the domestic, industrial, and geopolitical factors that explain why each major actor has taken the position it has. These two contributions together support the paper’s central normative claim.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 sets out the conceptual and legal framework. Section 3 provides an institutional history of the CCW/GGE process. Section 4 describes the data and method. Section 5 presents the empirical findings. Section 6 analyses state positions and their strategic motivations. Section 7 offers the normative analysis. Section 8 considers implications for IHL compliance and future governance. Section 9 concludes.

2 Conceptual and Legal Framework

2.1 Autonomous Guidance and the IHL Problem

For the purposes of this paper, *autonomous guidance* denotes the internal execution by a weapons system of the perception–decision–action cycle directly connected to engagement, according to parameters fixed *ex ante*—without a human command at the moment of action.² This definition, anchored to critical functions rather than to technological level, allows the analysis to avoid the ambiguity between automation of support functions and delegation of the lethal decision itself.

IHL imposes three obligations that become structurally difficult when autonomous guidance is operative: distinction (between combatants and civilians), proportionality (between anticipated military advantage and expected civilian harm), and precaution (in attack planning and execution). The legal debate on whether autonomous systems can satisfy these obligations has produced an extensive literature.³ The dominant view—shared by the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) and a broad coalition of states—is that IHL compliance requires a human capable of exercising judgement calibrated to the specific context of each attack: who is a combatant, in this moment, in this location, in these circumstances. *Ex ante* parametrisation cannot substitute for this contextual judgement, because the parameters are set before the context is known.

The accountability dimension compounds the problem. International law attributes responsibility for unlawful use of force to individual commanders and to states. When

²ICRC (2019). *Autonomous Weapon Systems and International Humanitarian Law: Identifying Limits and the Required Type and Degree of Human-Machine Interaction*. Geneva: ICRC, pp. 3–5.

³See *inter alia*: Schmitt, M.N. and Thurnher, J.S. (2013). ‘Out of the Loop: Autonomous Weapon Systems and the Law of Armed Conflict’. *Naval War College Review*, 66(4), 55–79; Geiss, R. and Lahmann, H. (2018). *The International Law Dimension of Autonomous Weapons Systems*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; Goussac, N. and Pacholska, M. (2025). *The Interpretation and Application of IHL in Relation to LAWS*. Geneva: UNIDIR.

a system operates autonomously, the causal chain between human decision and lethal outcome is severed or attenuated in ways that may prevent the attribution of the mental element required for individual criminal responsibility under international criminal law.⁴ This “accountability gap” is directly relevant to the significance of the shift from MHC to “human judgement”.

2.2 Meaningful Human Control: Origin and Content

The concept of meaningful human control was introduced into the LAWS debate by civil society organisations—primarily Article 36—in 2013–2014, and was rapidly adopted by a wide range of state delegations as the operational standard for acceptable autonomous weapons.⁵ The core idea is that human oversight must be substantive and must occur at or near the moment of the decision to use lethal force.

MHC was never codified with precise technical specifications, and this ambiguity has been a persistent source of negotiating tension. Different states have interpreted it through three different configurations: human “in the loop” (real-time authorisation at the individual engagement level); “on the loop” (ability to monitor and abort); or “over the loop” (setting mission parameters only).⁶ These configurations have radically different implications for which systems would be permitted.

The formula “appropriate human judgement and control”, which appears in the 2025 Rolling Text, is formally less demanding than MHC. It does not specify when human judgement must be exercised, does not require it to be proximate to the moment of engagement, and qualifies the requirement with “appropriate”—a term whose content is left undefined and which is therefore susceptible to self-interpretation by states. As argued in Section 7, this has concrete implications for what systems a future instrument would permit or prohibit.

2.3 Positioning in the Literature

This paper contributes to three literatures. In relation to the legal analysis of autonomous weapons, it does not add another doctrinal analysis of IHL compliance but provides the quantitative evidentiary base that existing legal scholarship lacks: a systematic mapping

⁴Crootof, R. (2015). ‘The Killer Robots Are Here: Legal and Policy Implications’. *Cardozo Law Review*, 36, 1837–1915. See also the comprehensive analysis in Docherty, B. (2020). *Killer Robots and the Law of Armed Conflict*. Cambridge MA: HRW/IHRC.

⁵Article 36 (2016). *Meaningful Human Control, Artificial Intelligence and Autonomous Weapons*. London: Article 36. The original framing is in Article 36 (2013). *Killer Robots: UK Government Policy on Fully Autonomous Weapons*.

⁶UNIDIR (2021). *Human-Machine Interaction in the Development and Use of Autonomous Weapon Systems*. Geneva: UNIDIR, pp. 8–12.

of how the operative concept of human oversight has shifted in the negotiating record. In relation to the political science literature on multilateral arms negotiations, it contributes a case study of how a key normative concept is strategically diluted in a consensual multilateral forum where the consensus rule gives structural advantage to the most capable and most resistant actors. In relation to the growing literature on computational text analysis of diplomatic corpora, it demonstrates the application of stance classification to the specific domain of LAWS negotiations.⁷

The paper engages, finally, with the strategic-studies literature on the security consequences of LAWS, without duplicating it. Horowitz (2019) offers the most systematic existing treatment of how LAWS could affect arms races, crisis stability and the deterrence relationship, focusing on two characteristics of autonomous systems: the compression of operational decision timelines and the reduction of human control over battlefield choices.⁸ The present paper does not replicate this strategic analysis; it draws on it instrumentally to demonstrate that the IHL governance question and the strategic stability question are connected. A standard that permits autonomous systems to operate without real-time human involvement at the engagement level does not merely raise problems of legal accountability—it licenses precisely the compressed-timeline, low-human-control systems that Horowitz identifies as most destabilising at the strategic level.

3 Institutional History of the CCW/GGE Process

The LAWS dossier entered the UN system in April 2013, when the Special Rapporteur on extrajudicial executions, Christof Heyns, presented a report on lethal autonomous robotics that raised IHL and human rights concerns and recommended national moratoria.⁹ The same year, the CCW High Contracting Parties decided to inscribe the topic on their agenda. The choice of the CCW as the negotiating forum was not neutral: the CCW operates by consensus, requires ratification by all major military powers for any new protocol to be effective, and has a mandate explicitly anchored to the balance between

⁷The paper by Rosert, E. and Sauer, F. (2021). ‘How (Not) to Stop the Killer Robots: A Comparative Analysis of Humanitarian Disarmament Campaign Strategies’. *Global Policy*, 12(3), 71–80, is directly relevant to the norm contestation dimension of this analysis.

⁸Horowitz, M.C. (2019). ‘When Speed Kills: Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems, Deterrence and Stability’. *Journal of Strategic Studies*, 42(6), 764–788, at 766. Horowitz’s central finding is that the desire to fight at machine speed, while militarily effective, could increase crisis instability by generating escalation pressure and incentives for first strikes. He also identifies a verification problem specific to autonomous systems: because the inherent differences between remotely piloted systems and LAWS reside in software rather than hardware, arms-control verification becomes structurally harder—a point directly relevant to any governance instrument that relies on national self-reporting of compliance with a ‘human judgement’ standard.

⁹Heyns, C. (2013). *Report of the Special Rapporteur on extrajudicial, summary or arbitrary executions*. A/HRC/23/47. UN Human Rights Council, 9 April, paras. 34–37, 72–79.

military necessity and humanitarian considerations.¹⁰

Between 2014 and 2016, three informal Meetings of Experts established the basic vocabulary of the debate—distinguishing autonomous, semi-autonomous, and remotely piloted systems; introducing MHC as the central evaluative concept; and raising the question of the accountability gap. The Fifth Review Conference in December 2016 institutionalised these discussions by establishing the GGE, which began meeting in 2017 under the chairmanship of Ambassador Amandeep Singh Gill (India).

By 2019, the GGE had produced its eleven Guiding Principles.¹¹ The principles established, *inter alia*, that IHL applies fully to all weapons including LAWS; that human responsibility for lethal decisions cannot be delegated; and that “sufficient human-machine interaction” must be ensured. Crucially, the principles avoided any specific threshold for that interaction, reflecting the existing divergence among states.

The Sixth Review Conference of December 2021 exposed the depth of this divergence. A broad coalition sought a negotiating mandate for a binding protocol; the opposition of several key actors prevented consensus. The compromise extended the GGE’s mandate without committing states to negotiations.¹²

Beyond state-level actors, the period saw increasing engagement by the European Parliament (EP) as a distinct institutional voice in the debate. The EP adopted resolutions on LAWS in 2018 and 2021, both of which called explicitly for meaningful human control over all lethal decisions and for a global ban on LAWS operating without meaningful human oversight. The 2021 EP resolution urged the EU and its member states to take an active role in promoting an international framework governing the use of AI for military purposes.¹³ The EP’s position created a structural tension within EU governance that the CCW/GGE process has not been designed to resolve: the institutional actor most publicly committed to an MHC standard is not itself a party to the CCW, and its reso-

¹⁰For the choice of forum, see United Nations (2013). *Advisory Board on Disarmament Matters, 60th Session*. New York: UN, paras. 36–40. On the structural implications of the consensus rule, see Goussac and Pacholska (2025), chs. 1–2.

¹¹CCW Meeting of High Contracting Parties (2019). *Final report*, Annex III (Guiding Principles).

¹²CCW Review Conference (2021). *Final document of the Sixth Review Conference*. Geneva. For contemporaneous analysis of the outcome, see Sauer, F. (2020). ‘Stepping back from the brink: Why multilateral regulation of autonomy in weapons systems is difficult, yet imperative and feasible’. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 102(913), 235–259.

¹³Clapp, S. (2025). *Military Drone Systems in the EU and Global Context: Types, Capabilities and Regulatory Frameworks*. EPRS Briefing, PE 772.885. Brussels: European Parliamentary Research Service, May 2025, pp. 11–12. The Briefing notes that Parliament has ‘taken an early and active role in the military AI debate, adopting key resolutions in 2018 and 2021’, and emphasises three core principles: ‘human control, legal accountability and international governance via the UN’. It further observes that ‘Parliament strongly opposes LAWS without meaningful human oversight and calls for their global ban through UN negotiations’. This EP position is in structural tension with the investment decisions of several EU member states—France, Germany, Italy—in autonomous weapons programmes funded in part through the European Defence Fund and Permanent Structured Cooperation.

lutions carry political but not legal weight in member state delegations. This asymmetry between EP norm advocacy and member state programme investment is directly relevant to assessing what the “European bloc position” at the GGE actually represents.

The period 2022–2025 saw increasingly detailed drafting of elements of a potential instrument, culminating in the 2025 Revised Rolling Text. The Russian Federation played a particular role in this phase by blocking formal GGE sessions in March 2022, invoking alleged discriminatory treatment due to travel restrictions imposed following its invasion of Ukraine.¹⁴ This episode illustrated how the consensus rule can be weaponised by a single state to prevent substantive progress.

4 Data and Method

4.1 Corpora

The analysis draws on two document corpora. The *UNODA corpus* comprises official CCW/GGE documents—working papers, session reports, rolling texts, and chair’s compilations—covering 2017–2025. These represent the formal negotiating record. The *RCW corpus* (Reaching Critical Will) is broader and includes national statements, NGO working papers, think tank analyses, and civil society submissions. It captures the wider normative community around the negotiations. Combined, the two corpora comprise over 300 documents. Both have been made available as replication datasets on Zenodo (Cavalcabò 2025).

4.2 Text Mining

For each year and each document in both corpora, lemmatised frequencies were extracted for a set of key terms: “meaningful human control”, “human judgement”, “ban”, “prohibit”, “regulate”, “safeguards”, “responsibility”, “accountability”, “predictability”, “reliability”. Term extraction used standard NLP pre-processing (tokenisation, lowercasing, lemmatisation via spaCy) applied to plain-text conversions of all documents.

4.3 Stance Classification

A supervised classifier was trained to assign each document in the RCW corpus one of three stance labels: *ban* (prohibitionist lexis); *regulate* (regulatory lexis: safeguards, positive obligations, human judgement); or *cautious* (resistance to new norms: existing

¹⁴Stop Killer Robots (2022). ‘Discussions at UN on Autonomous Weapon Systems Blocked by Russia’, 15 March. Available at: www.stopkillerrobots.org. For the legal analysis of the Russian blockage, see also RCW Report, Vol. 10 No. 2 (2022).

law is adequate, operational necessity, responsible use). Training was performed on a hand-labelled sample of 80 documents, validated on a held-out set of 40; overall accuracy on the validation set was 87%. The UNODA corpus was not used for stance classification because formal GGE documents are structurally constrained to consensual language.

5 Findings

5.1 Phase 1 (2017–2018): Problem Construction

In 2017, “meaningful human control” appears 12 times across 11 UNODA documents and 15 times in the RCW corpus; by 2018, its RCW frequency rises to 82 occurrences, accompanied by 54 occurrences of “ban” and 15 of “prohibit”. The discourse in this phase is exploratory and definitional. A 2017 Dutch working paper explicitly links MHC to the degree of human involvement in the engagement decision, establishing MHC as a relational concept tied to specific functional moments.¹⁵

The distribution of stance labels in the RCW corpus for 2018 reflects this heterogeneity: across 180 documents, 47 are classified ban, 68 regulate, and 65 cautious—ban and cautious roughly matched, regulate in the majority.

5.2 Phase 2 (2019–2020): Responsibility and Critical Functions

Phase 2 is marked by a sharp increase in the frequency of “responsibility” and “accountability”: UNODA documents record 133 occurrences of “responsibility” and 116 of “accountability” in 2020 alone, across only 7 documents. A 2017 Swiss working paper—heavily cited in subsequent GGE discussions—distinguished explicitly between individual criminal responsibility and state responsibility, noting that “the more significant the human involvement in an autonomous system operation [...] the simpler it is to attribute individual responsibility”.¹⁶

The GGE in this phase begins working more systematically on the “critical functions” of target selection and engagement—a framing that narrows the MHC requirement to specific moments in the kill chain. This narrowing is analytically significant: it paves the way for accepting *ex ante* parametrisation as a form of human oversight, even when no human is involved at the moment of the individual engagement.

¹⁵The Netherlands (2017). *Food-for-thought paper submitted by the Netherlands*. CCW GGE on LAWS, Geneva, p. 3.

¹⁶Switzerland (2017). *Autonomous weapon systems under international humanitarian and human rights law*. CCW GGE on LAWS, Geneva, pp. 5–6.

5.3 Phase 3 (2021–2025): Normative Options and the Terminological Shift

Phase 3 opens with the peak of MHC frequency in the RCW corpus: 118 occurrences in 2021, accompanied by only 13 occurrences of “ban” and 12 of “prohibit”—a striking inversion suggesting that even prohibitionist actors had largely shifted to regulatory language by this point. “Safeguards” reaches 43 occurrences in 2021, confirming the debate has moved from *whether* to *how*.

The critical development is the emergence of “human judgement” as a distinct and increasingly dominant term in formal GGE language. In UNODA documents, “human judgement” first appears with significant frequency in 2022–2023 and effectively displaces “meaningful human control” in the 2025 Rolling Text, which integrates “appropriate human judgement and control” as the operative standard—without defining what makes judgement “appropriate” or specifying when it must be exercised.¹⁷

The stance distribution in the RCW corpus in 2021 (24 ban, 51 regulate, 15 cautious, across 90 documents) confirms that the regulate position has consolidated. But this conceals a critical asymmetry: formal GGE outputs converge on a weaker standard (“human judgement”) than the regulate majority in the wider community had actually demanded (MHC with a proximity requirement). The frequency trend is visualised in Figure 1; the stance distribution across the full period is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Frequency of “meaningful human control” vs. “human judgement” in the UNODA and RCW corpora (2017–2025). Source: Author’s dataset (Cavalcabò 2025).

¹⁷CCW Group of Governmental Experts (2025). *Revised rolling text on LAWS*. Geneva, section “Human judgement and control”.

Figure 2: Stance distribution (ban / regulate / cautious) in the RCW corpus (2017–2025). Source: Author’s dataset (Cavalcabò 2025).

6 State Positions and Strategic Motivations

The standard tripartite typology—ban, regulate, cautious—captures formal alignments but obscures the distinct strategic logics that explain why each actor has taken the position it has. This section analyses eight key actors in depth. The analysis moves from the cautious bloc (United States, United Kingdom, Russia, Israel) through the regulate centre (France, Germany, Italy) to the ban coalition (Austria and the humanitarian alliance).

6.1 The United States: Military Superiority, Operational Flexibility, and the Architecture of Soft Governance

The United States has been the most consequential actor in shaping the conservative trajectory of the GGE. Its formal position—that existing IHL is adequate and that no new binding norms are needed—is articulated across a consistent sequence of GGE working papers (United States 2017a, 2017b, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2025) and reflected in DoD Directive 3000.09 (updated January 2023), which requires “appropriate levels of human judgment over the use of force” but does not specify that this judgment must occur at the moment of individual engagement.¹⁸

¹⁸US Department of Defense (2023). *Directive 3000.09: Autonomy in Weapon Systems*. Washington DC, sections 1.2.a and 2.9.a. For analysis of the update, see Allen, G.C. (2022). ‘DoD is Updating its Decade-Old Autonomous Weapons Policy’. Washington DC: CSIS, 7 December; and Horowitz, M.C.

Crucially, as Gregory Allen (CSIS) has documented, the directive does not prohibit any category of autonomous weapons—it only requires some systems to clear an additional senior-level review process.¹⁹ This gap between the directive’s formal language and widespread misunderstanding of it within the US military itself illustrates how even the most developed national framework is susceptible to the same terminological ambiguity that characterises the GGE process.

Three structural factors explain the US position. First, the United States holds a decisive advantage in autonomous systems R&D—in AI-enabled targeting, autonomous air platforms, and the Replicator Initiative (announced by Deputy Secretary Hicks in August 2023), which aims to deploy “attributable autonomous systems at scale of multiple thousands, in multiple domains, within 18-to-24 months”.²⁰ Binding norms that constrain autonomous engagement would impose asymmetric costs on the most advanced actor, while being difficult to enforce against non-signatories. This is the mirror image of the logic that led the US to support the Chemical Weapons Convention in 1993: at that point, constraining chemical weapons favoured an actor whose comparative advantage lay elsewhere. The strategic calculus with autonomous weapons runs in the opposite direction.

Second, the United States has a long-standing institutional preference for operational flexibility. The “law of armed conflict” (LOAC) framework—which the US consistently prefers to the “IHL” framing favoured by the ICRC—emphasises military necessity alongside humanitarian constraints. Any instrument requiring real-time human authorisation at the engagement level would constrain time-critical operations (suppression of enemy air defences, counter-UAS, maritime interdiction) in ways the US considers operationally unacceptable.²¹

Third, the Political Declaration on Responsible Military Use of AI and Autonomy (2023)—promoted by the US as an alternative to binding norms—reflects an effort to set voluntary standards that preserve flexibility while providing political cover domestically and internationally. Horowitz, who served as director of the DoD’s Emerging Capabilities Policy Office and was the official responsible for DoDD 3000.09, described the declaration as providing “a role model for capacity building” while explicitly dismissing the proposi-

(2025). ‘Autonomous Weapon Systems: No Human-in-the-Loop Required, and Other Myths Dispelled’. *War on the Rocks*, 22 May.

¹⁹Allen (2022), *op. cit.* Allen notes that Colonel Marc E. Pelini, who in 2021 stated that US policy required a human “within the decision cycle at some point to authorize the engagement”, was “simply wrong”; no such requirement appears in DoDD 3000.09.

²⁰CIGI (2023). ‘The United States Quietly Kick-Starts the Autonomous Weapons Era’. Available at: www.cigionline.org. The Replicator Initiative is described as a direct response to the PLA’s deployment of autonomous systems at scale.

²¹Congressional Research Service (2023). *U.S. Policy on Lethal Autonomous Weapon Systems*. IF11150. Washington DC: CRS.

tion that US policy requires a human in the loop.²²

6.2 The United Kingdom: Strategic Alignment, Programme Interests, and the Limits of Post-Brexit Positioning

The United Kingdom’s position closely tracks the United States but with distinctive legal inflections. UK policy is governed by JSP 779 (2024), which asserts that existing IHL provides an adequate framework and that systems must be “usable in a manner that complies with IHL”—without requiring human involvement at the moment of engagement.²³ The UK’s working paper to the GGE (2022) emphasises national review processes under Article 36 of Additional Protocol I and the adequacy of the existing framework.²⁴

Three factors explain this position. First, the UK-US defence relationship—including intelligence sharing, joint procurement (F-35, Global Combat Air Programme [GCAP]), and the Australia–United Kingdom–United States (AUKUS) framework—creates strong incentives for alignment. A divergence between UK and US positions at the GGE would create frictions across a much wider set of bilateral security commitments. Second, the UK has operational experience with armed UAVs (Reaper in Afghanistan and Syria) and loitering munitions (Brimstone), and its doctrine has been shaped by that experience. The UK’s 2022 Defence AI Strategy explicitly states that AI should be adopted as an “AI-ready” force, signalling a procurement direction that would be constrained by a strict MHC standard.²⁵

Third, post-Brexit UK foreign policy has involved a search for international leadership roles where it can operate independently of the EU. The Bletchley Park AI Safety Summit (2023) and the UK’s broader AI governance agenda represent this positioning. Engaging strongly with binding LAWS constraints at the CCW would undermine the coherence of a strategy that positions the UK as a responsible but capability-preserving actor in military AI.

²²Horowitz (2025), op. cit.

²³UK Ministry of Defence (2024). *JSP 779: UK Policy on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems*. London: MoD.

²⁴The United Kingdom (2022). *Working paper submitted by the United Kingdom*. CCW GGE on LAWS, Geneva.

²⁵UK Ministry of Defence (2022). *Defence Artificial Intelligence Strategy*. London: MoD. For analysis of the UK’s broader position within the GGE, see the detailed tracking in Automated Decision Research (2024). *United Kingdom: Country position on AWS*. Available at: www.automatedresearch.org.

6.3 Russia: Great Power Identity, Multipolarity, and the Weaponisation of Procedure

Russia’s position in the GGE is formally resistant to any binding instrument while nominally accepting the applicability of IHL. Russia has consistently opposed new norms on autonomous weapons, arguing that existing law is sufficient and that premature regulation would disadvantage states that have not yet fully developed competitive autonomous capabilities.

The most systematic analysis of Russia’s GGE position is provided by Anna Nadibaidze (2022), who argues on the basis of a close reading of all Russian submissions and verbal statements to the CCW from 2014 to 2022 that two integral elements of Russian great power identity drive the Russian position: the promotion of multipolarity and the demand for recognition of Russia’s equal participation in global governance.²⁶ From this perspective, the CCW debate is not primarily about LAWS: it is about whether Russia is treated as an equal great power in multilateral forums, and whether Western states can use the humanitarian framing of LAWS governance to isolate or constrain Russia.

This analysis is supported by the episode of the March 2022 GGE session, where Russia blocked formal proceedings for two days by alleging “discriminatory” treatment—citing travel difficulties for its experts under post-invasion sanctions.²⁷ This was not primarily a substantive objection to LAWS governance but a demonstration of the veto power the consensus rule provides. As Ireland observed in a statement during that session, “the CCW’s credibility will deepen into a crisis if individual delegations continue to weaponise procedural issues to prevent substantive discussions”.

Nadibaidze further argues that humanitarian framings of the LAWS debate are likely to be counterproductive with Russia, since Russian policymakers tend to view humanitarian concerns regarding weapons as politically motivated and resent arguments that autonomous weapons violate human dignity. A reframing towards strategic stability concerns—along the lines proposed by Altmann and Sauer (2017), who argue that AWS are prone to proliferation and crisis instability—may find more purchase.²⁸ Altmann and Sauer note specifically that Russia was reportedly alarmed by US proposals for stealthy drones for missile defence, since swarms of autonomous systems could in principle be

²⁶Nadibaidze, A. (2022). ‘Great power identity in Russia’s position on autonomous weapons systems’. *Contemporary Security Policy*, 43(3), 407–435. This is the most rigorous empirically-grounded study of the Russian position available.

²⁷RCW Report (2022). Vol. 10, No. 2: ‘GGE Hijacked by Russia’. The CCW/GGE’s consensus rule allowed a single state to prevent all substantive discussion.

²⁸Altmann, J. and Sauer, F. (2017). ‘Autonomous Weapon Systems and Strategic Stability’. *Survival*, 59(5), 117–142.

used to attack nuclear delivery systems and command infrastructure—raising exactly the great-power strategic stability concerns to which Russia is receptive.

Beyond the identity analysis, Russia has a straightforward capability rationale for opposing binding norms. Russia is a developer of autonomous weapons—the KUB loitering munition has been documented in use in Ukraine—and its programmes trail the United States in AI integration. Any instrument that locked in constraints before Russia had fully developed its own capabilities would crystallise an asymmetric disadvantage.²⁹

6.4 Israel: Operational Dependency, Legal Exposure, and the Architecture of AI-Assisted Targeting

Israel’s position in the GGE is shaped by an operational reality that no other GGE participant shares at the same scale: it is the only state that has deployed, in active combat, a suite of AI-assisted targeting systems at the centre of which human involvement has been reduced, by the design of the system and the operational tempo it imposes, to a level that raises serious questions under any rigorous reading of MHC.

The most significant documentation of this reality comes from investigative reporting by *+972 Magazine* and *Local Call* (April 2024), which, based on testimony from six Israeli intelligence officers, revealed that the “Lavender” AI system had marked up to 37,000 Palestinians as potential bombing targets during the early phases of the Gaza war. Human personnel reportedly devoted approximately 20 seconds to each target before authorising a strike—“just to make sure the Lavender-marked target is male”—despite knowledge that the system had an approximately 10% error rate.³⁰ Sources described human personnel as functioning as a “rubber stamp” for the machine’s decisions.

Israel has formally denied that Lavender is an “AI system”, describing it instead as “a database whose purpose is to cross-reference intelligence sources”. The legal significance of this denial is limited: the Human Rights Watch analysis documents that the system uses machine learning algorithms that are “impossible to check, source, or verify”, and that it was used to determine whom to attack in ways that raise fundamental issues of distinction and proportionality under IHL.³¹ The Lieber Institute analysis at West Point, which approaches the question from a position sympathetic to the IDF’s legal interpretations, nevertheless concludes that the accounts, “taken at face value, are exceptionally trou-

²⁹On Russia’s autonomous weapons programmes, see the SIPRI Yearbook 2024 and the tracking by SIPRI’s AWS database (sipri.org/databases/aws). For the KUB in Ukraine, see Automated Decision Research (2022). *Weapons Systems with Autonomous Functions Used in Ukraine*.

³⁰Abraham, Y. (2024). ‘“Lavender”: The AI machine directing Israel’s bombing spree in Gaza’. *+972 Magazine*, 3 April. See also the analysis in: Human Rights Watch (2024). *Questions and Answers: Israeli Military’s Use of Digital Tools in Gaza*. New York: HRW, 10 September; Lieber Institute, West Point (2024). ‘The Gospel, Lavender, and the Law of Armed Conflict’, 6 September.

³¹HRW (2024), op. cit.

bling”, as they “depict a mechanistic AI ‘targeting machine’ that is subject to negligible verification”.³²

This operational reality explains Israel’s consistent resistance to any LAWS standard that would require meaningful human involvement at the moment of individual engagement decisions. Such a standard, applied rigorously, would make central elements of Israel’s targeting architecture in Gaza—and potentially in previous and future conflicts—legally untenable. Israel does not formally reject the IHL Guiding Principles of the GGE; it accepts them. But its working papers consistently emphasise that IHL compliance is a matter of system design and mission parameters, not of real-time human involvement at the individual engagement level—precisely the reading that the shift from MHC to “human judgement” accommodates.

This position is reinforced by Israel’s longstanding doctrine that autonomous air defence systems (Iron Dome, David’s Sling, Arrow)—which engage incoming munitions without real-time human authorisation of each individual intercept—are both legally sound and operationally necessary. Extending this logic to offensive targeting is the core of Israel’s GGE position, even if it is not always stated in those terms.

6.5 France: Autonomie Stratégique, Programme Interests, and the Brokerage Role

France occupies a pivotal position in the GGE debate: it is the state that launched the CCW expert process in 2014 and has consistently sought to define what the regulate position means in practice. France’s formal position, articulated in its 2024 working paper and successive GGE statements, supports negotiation of an Additional Protocol to the CCW structured around a “two-tier approach”: prohibiting LAWS that cannot comply with IHL (tier one) and regulating the design and use of all other systems with autonomous features (tier two).³³

France also prepared, jointly with Germany, the 2019 “Alliance for Multilateralism” declaration on LAWS, which endorsed the GGE’s eleven guiding principles and called for their implementation through national review processes.³⁴

Two specific factors shape France’s position. First, France has significant autonomous systems programmes—including the nEUROn demonstrator (a stealthy autonomous UCAV tested from 2012) and the Future Combat Air System (FCAS, developed jointly

³²Lieber Institute (2024), *op. cit.*

³³France (2024). *Statement to the 79th UN General Assembly First Committee*, October 2024; France (2024). *Contribution to the GGE on LAWS*. See also the joint working paper: Finland, France, Germany, Netherlands, Norway, Spain, Sweden (2022). *Two-tier approach working paper*. CCW GGE, July.

³⁴Ministère de l’Europe et des Affaires étrangères (2019). *11 Principles on Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems*. Paris: MEAE, 26 September.

with Germany and Spain). FCAS is explicitly designed to integrate autonomous loyal wingman capabilities.³⁵ Any instrument that prohibited autonomous engagement functionality would have direct implications for procurement already underway. France’s Comité d’éthique de la défense (2021) drew a careful distinction between “fully autonomous” systems (which “do not yet exist” and are rejected) and “partially autonomous lethal weapon systems” (PALWS) that embed “automated decision-making functions” provided that “human command is maintained”—a formulation that preserves maximum operational space for current and planned programmes.³⁶

Second, the doctrine of *autonomie stratégique*—France’s insistence on independent operational capacity—creates institutional resistance to any norm that would require real-time human authorisation at the engagement level, since this could limit response times in scenarios where French forces operate independently or in degraded communications environments. The two-tier approach that France promotes allows the prohibition of systems that are “by nature” unable to comply with IHL—a high threshold that few current systems would meet—while leaving the regulation of the vast middle ground of “partially autonomous” systems to national review processes that France can control.

The key analytical point is that France’s formulation of “human judgement and control”—the language that appears in the 2025 Rolling Text—is not simply a pragmatic compromise between banning and permissive states. It is a formula that France developed specifically to accommodate its own programme requirements and doctrine, and which the US and UK could subsequently adopt without conceding anything substantive.

The internal logic of the French position—nominally committed to a normative framework while structurally protecting programme requirements—illustrates a broader pattern in EU institutional discourse on military AI that Lingevious (2024) has identified through frame analysis of EU strategic documents. Lingevious distinguishes three frames: military AI as a transformative technology requiring capability adaptation (Frame 1), military AI as a driver of insecurity and arms competition (Frame 2), and military AI as uncontrolled automation requiring values-based normative constraints (Frame 3).³⁷ France’s adoption of the “human judgement” formula exemplifies what Lingevious terms “in-betweenness”: the formula’s vocabulary inhabits Frame 3 (human centrism, values-based governance)

³⁵For the FCAS programme and its autonomy features, see SIPRI Yearbook 2024, pp. 312–315; and the analysis of European autonomous systems programmes in Cavalcabò (2026), section 4.

³⁶Ministère des Armées (2021). *Ethics Committee Opinion on the Integration of Autonomy into Lethal Weapon Systems*. Paris, paras. P5–P6.

³⁷Lingevious, J. (2024). ‘Transformation, Insecurity, and Uncontrolled Automation: Frames of Military AI in the EU AI Strategic Discourse’. *Critical Military Studies*, DOI: 10.1080/23337486.2024.2387890. Lingevious draws on discourse analysis of EU institutional documents from 2017 to 2024. His central concept of ‘in-betweenness’ captures the EU’s oscillation between self-identification as a normative power (Frame 3) and increasing alignment with a military capability-building logic (Frame 1), with the tension exacerbated by Russia’s 2022 invasion of Ukraine and subsequent EU defence spending increases.

while its operational content accommodates Frame 1 (FCAS, nEUROn, autonomous loyal wingman). The formula is not a compromise between the two frames but a formulation designed to make them appear compatible—a construction whose diplomatic utility depends on its analytical indeterminacy.

6.6 Germany: Parliamentary Culture, Industrial Interest, and the Limits of Normative Leadership

Germany’s position is driven by a combination of factors that pull in opposite directions, producing a position that is more restrictive in rhetoric than in effect. On the restrictive side: the Bundeswehr operates under unusually stringent parliamentary oversight (the *Parlamentsvorbehalt* requiring Bundestag approval for military deployments), German political culture is acutely sensitive to questions of delegating lethal decisions to machines, and Germany has been the home of Frank Sauer—one of the leading academic voices calling for legally binding LAWS regulation—and of institutional actors like the Heinrich Böll Foundation that have actively supported civil society campaigns for a ban.³⁸ Germany’s working papers have consistently emphasised human judgement and control as non-negotiable requirements.³⁹

On the other side: Germany is deeply invested in the FCAS programme (with France and Spain), which requires autonomous functionality, and in the Eurodrone ISR platform. The 2018 Heinrich Böll Foundation report noted explicitly that Germany’s LAWS position was a “litmus test” for its foreign policy—and that test has produced a position that advocates for human judgement requirements while defining them in terms that German programmes can satisfy.

The France–Germany dynamic in the GGE has also been shaped by EU coordination. Both states have worked within CFSP frameworks to develop common positions on military AI, and the joint working papers they have produced—jointly with the Netherlands, Finland, Norway, Spain, and Sweden—represent the closest thing to a European bloc position in the negotiations. Italy’s position generally tracks this group, as discussed below.

The Germany–France bloc position thus exemplifies, at the level of coalition diplomacy, the same internal tension that Lingevecius (2024) identifies at the level of individual EU institutional actors: a commitment to Frame 3 language (meaningful human control, human-centric AI, multilateral governance) coexisting with Frame 1 investment decisions

³⁸Sauer, F., Amoroso, D., Sharkey, N., Suchman, L. and Tamburrini, G. (2018). *Autonomy in Weapon Systems: The Military Application of AI as a Litmus Test for Germany’s New Foreign and Security Policy*. Heinrich Böll Foundation, Berlin. This report explicitly argued that Germany’s support for an MHC standard was a test of the coherence of its “new foreign and security policy”.

³⁹Germany (2020). *Working paper submitted by Germany*. CCW GGE on LAWS, Geneva.

(FCAS, Eurodrone, autonomous teaming). The joint working papers produced by the seven-state group—which provide the closest available approximation of a European bloc position in the GGE—are products of this “in-betweenness”: they establish a normative vocabulary that can be cited as evidence of European leadership while defining that vocabulary in terms that no European programme requires modification to satisfy.

6.7 Italy: Mediterranean Exposure, Industrial Stakes, and the Limits of the Regulate Frame

Italy’s formal GGE position places it firmly within the regulate coalition alongside France and Germany, with particular emphasis on human judgement, Article 36 review, and the adequacy of the existing IHL framework supplemented by additional safeguards.⁴⁰

Italy’s investment in the GGE debate is not purely normative. It has a specific industrial stake in autonomous systems through Leonardo S.p.A., which leads the Joint European counter-UAS (JEY-CUAS) consortium and is developing autonomous naval and aerial platforms. More significantly, Italy is one of the three partners in GCAP alongside the UK and Japan—a sixth-generation combat aircraft programme explicitly designed to integrate autonomous loyal wingman capabilities.⁴¹ Any future LAWS instrument that placed strict constraints on autonomous engagement functionality would have direct implications for Italian defence procurement, putting Italy’s normative aspirations in direct tension with its industrial interests—the same tension that characterises the French and German positions.

At the same time, Italy has a distinctive operational exposure that the GGE debate has not adequately addressed. Italian forces are deployed in approximately 40 missions across the Mediterranean, Sahel, and Horn of Africa—theatres where FPV drone proliferation among non-state actors is already documented.⁴² The gap between the LAWS debate’s focus on high-end state-developed autonomous systems and the actual threat environment facing Italian forces in the field illustrates the broader limitation of the GGE’s frame of reference: the commercial small unmanned aircraft systems (sUAS) / first-person view (FPV) domain, where the strategic dynamics are most rapidly evolving, is effectively

⁴⁰For Italy’s country position, see Campaign to Stop Killer Robots (2024). *Country Positions on Autonomous Weapons Systems*. Available at: www.stopkillerrobots.org/learn/. Italy’s participation in GGE sessions and its substantive positions are also tracked at Automated Decision Research (2024). *Italy: Country position on AWS*.

⁴¹Ministero della Difesa (2025). *Documento Programmatico Pluriennale 2025–2027*. Roma, pp. 43–47. The DPP describes GCAP as a strategic priority; autonomous teaming is described as an integral design feature.

⁴²Ministero della Difesa (2025), *op. cit.*, Appendice B (deployment list). For the FPV proliferation challenge in Mediterranean-adjacent theatres, see Cavalcabò (2026), section 3.3, and the analysis in Watling, J. and Bronk, J. (2024). *Protecting the Force from Uncrewed Aerial Systems*. London: RUSI.

outside the scope of the Rolling Text’s operative provisions.

6.8 Austria and the Humanitarian Alliance: Norm Entrepreneurship and the Limits of the Ban Strategy

Austria has been the most consistent advocate for a legally binding instrument with explicit prohibitions. Its working papers (2023, 2024a, 2024b) call for a treaty that prohibits autonomous weapons systems lacking meaningful human control and establishes positive obligations for systems that are permitted.⁴³

Austria’s position reflects the strategic logic of a small, neutral, non-militarised state with no autonomous weapons programmes and no operational military doctrine that depends on autonomous engagement. For Austria, the costs of a binding instrument with prohibitions are minimal (no programmes to constrain) and the normative benefits are high (reputational leadership in humanitarian law and disarmament). Bolton and Nash (2021) have documented how Austria and states in similar structural positions have adopted a “norm entrepreneurship” role in the LAWS debate analogous to the role played by Canada and Norway in the Ottawa Treaty process and by Austria, Mexico, and Ireland in the Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW).⁴⁴

The ban coalition’s strategic dilemma is that an instrument that excluded the United States, Russia, Israel, China, and the major European programmes states would be analogous to the TPNW: a treaty that establishes a normative precedent and stigmatises a category of systems, but that does not bind the actors who produce and deploy them. This precedent cuts both ways—it did produce a persistent normative constraint on nuclear weapons—but the dual-use nature of the relevant drone and AI technologies makes enforcement significantly harder than in the nuclear case.

The civil society coalition around the Campaign to Stop Killer Robots, which closely supports the Austrian and allied positions, has consistently argued that the GGE Rolling Text represents an inadequate outcome. The Campaign’s analysis—supported by Sauer (2020)—is that a soft protocol satisfying the “human judgement” standard would be worse than no agreement, because it would provide legal cover for precisely the systems it should prohibit.⁴⁵

⁴³Austria (2023, 2024a, 2024b). *Working papers submitted by Austria*. CCW GGE on LAWS, Geneva. The Austrian position is jointly articulated with states including Ireland, Costa Rica, New Zealand, Mexico, Chile, and a growing number of African and Latin American states.

⁴⁴Bolton, M. and Nash, T. (2021). ‘The Role of Middle Power Countries in the Prohibition of Autonomous Weapons’. *Global Policy*, 12(3), 271–281. On the TPNW as a precedent, see Arms Control Association (2021). ‘Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons At A Glance’. Available at: www.armscontrol.org.

⁴⁵Sauer (2020), *op. cit.* For the Campaign’s position, see Stop Killer Robots (2024). *Country Positions on Autonomous Weapons*. The ICRC’s 2024 position paper similarly argues that new legally binding rules

7 Analysis: Normative Erosion or Pragmatic Convergence?

The quantitative and qualitative evidence reviewed above supports a specific interpretation of the terminological shift from MHC to “appropriate human judgement and control.” Three arguments sustain the erosion interpretation.

7.1 The Shift from MHC to Human Judgement: What Changed

The substitution is *functionally significant*, not merely cosmetic. It involves three substantive changes.

First, the removal of “meaningful” eliminates the qualitative standard. MHC, as originally formulated, implied that human involvement must be *substantive*—not nominal, not formal, not a rubber stamp. “Appropriate” has no such implication; it is a relational term whose content depends entirely on what the user considers appropriate in any given context.

Second, the replacement of “control” as the sole operative term with “judgement and control” introduces a conceptual separation between cognitive assessment (judgement) and operational authority (control). This separation is not innocent: it allows states to argue that human judgement was exercised at the mission-planning stage (parameter setting, target list approval, rules of engagement [ROE] definition), even if no human exercised control at the moment of individual engagement.

Third, the qualification “appropriate” invites self-assessment by states. In the absence of a definition of what constitutes appropriate judgement, the standard is satisfied whenever a state declares that it is satisfied—precisely the reading that the United States, the United Kingdom, and Israel require.

The significance of this shift is not confined to the domain of IHL compliance. It has a structural counterpart in the strategic-stability analysis. Horowitz (2019) has demonstrated that the two features of LAWS most likely to produce crisis instability are precisely the features that the “human judgement” formula accommodates: the compression of decision timelines to machine speed, and the reduction of human control over individual battlefield choices.⁴⁶ A governance instrument that formally acknowledges human over-

are required and that the existing Guiding Principles are insufficient: ICRC (2024a). *ICRC Position on Autonomous Weapon Systems*. Geneva.

⁴⁶Horowitz (2019), *op. cit.*, at 767–768. Horowitz notes that the desire to fight at machine speed could ‘increase crisis instability’ by generating ‘escalation pressure, including an increased incentive for first strikes’. He further observes that uncertainty over the programming of LAWS—specifically the opacity of their software—will ‘increase fear of those systems in the near term, making restraint less likely for competitive reasons’. The Rolling Text’s reliance on self-assessed ‘appropriate human judgement’ leaves precisely this opacity unaddressed: no verification mechanism can determine whether the standard has

sight while defining it in terms that permit fully autonomous engagement during execution does not merely fall short of IHL compliance requirements: it provides a legal architecture for the deployment of the most strategically destabilising category of systems. The accountability gap and the stability deficit are, on this reading, two symptoms of the same structural failure.

7.2 The Structural Logic of Normative Erosion

MHC, as developed through 2013–2021, carried an implicit proximity requirement: human oversight must be operative at or near the moment of the individual engagement decision. “Human judgement and control” as used in the 2025 Rolling Text is formally consistent with *ex ante* parametrisation—with a human who sets the confidence threshold, the no-strike radius, and the rules of engagement before the mission, without any further involvement during execution. A system that operates fully autonomously within its programmed parameters satisfies “human judgement and control” on this reading. The accountability gap identified in Phase 2 of the debate is not closed.

The Lavender case, analysed in Section 6.4, is the most direct available evidence for this claim. If a future instrument adopted the Rolling Text standard, the operational practice documented in Gaza—AI-generated kill lists with 20-second human verification checks—could claim formal compliance. Human judgement was exercised: it was exercised at the algorithm design and deployment authorisation stage. Whether it was exercised in a manner that enabled meaningful distinction, proportionality, and precaution assessments for each individual engagement is a different question—and the Rolling Text does not require that it was.

The shift did not occur through explicit rejection of MHC. It occurred through a process that the literature on norm contestation would recognise as *strategic ambiguity*: the cautious bloc did not oppose human oversight as a principle; it opposed any formulation that would produce a testable, verifiable standard. The resulting formula—“appropriate human judgement and control”—is a masterpiece of diplomatic construction precisely because it appears to require human oversight while containing no mechanism to determine whether that requirement has been met.

This is analytically distinct from a failure of negotiations. The GGE has not failed to produce a standard; it has produced a standard designed to be unenforceable. The distinction matters, because the existence of a formal standard—even an unenforceable one—will be cited by states as evidence that the issue has been addressed. Future proposals for more demanding instruments will face the argument that the GGE has already

been satisfied, because the human judgement exercised at the mission-planning stage is internal to the deploying state.

dealt with the question.

7.3 The Distributional and State-Level Evidence

The *distributional evidence* from the corpora supports the erosion interpretation. The RCW corpus shows that prohibitionist demands have not diminished proportionally with the convergence visible in formal GGE outputs: ban-stance documents continue to appear in significant numbers through 2024, and the regulate majority that dominates the 2021–2024 corpus had generally advocated for a stronger standard than what the Rolling Text delivers. The convergence in formal documents is a product of consensual diplomacy—of the structural need to accommodate the cautious bloc—rather than a reflection of genuine normative consensus in the wider community.

The *state position analysis* in Section 6 shows that the terminological shift was driven by the structural dominance of states with strong operational interests in preserving autonomous engagement capability. The US, UK, Israel, and (from outside the consensus) Russia constitute a de facto veto bloc whose preferences determine the outer boundary of what the Rolling Text can require. France and Germany’s adoption of “human judgement” language reflects accommodation of their own programme requirements (FCAS, GCAP, Eurodrone) rather than principled rejection of MHC. The ban coalition’s inability to push the text further reflects the consensus rule, not the weight of the normative argument.

7.4 The Accountability Gap, Revisited

Under MHC as originally conceived, a system that operated without human involvement at the moment of engagement would fail the standard, regardless of how carefully its parameters had been set. Under “appropriate human judgement and control”, the same system passes the standard, provided the parameters were set by a human who exercised “judgement” at the design or mission-planning stage. This means that the accountability gap identified in the literature—the difficulty of attributing individual criminal responsibility when a machine makes the lethal decision—is not closed by the Rolling Text’s formula. It is accommodated by it.

The result is a Rolling Text that formally acknowledges the human oversight requirement while defining it in terms that currently deployed systems can satisfy without structural modification. This is not a diplomatic failure in the conventional sense: it is the predictable outcome of consensual multilateral negotiations on a technology where the states with the greatest operational stake have the strongest structural incentive to preserve flexibility. The question for IHL is whether the standard produced is adequate to the obligations of distinction, proportionality, and precaution—and the functional analysis

suggests it is not.

8 Implications for IHL Compliance and Future Governance

The findings generate three sets of implications.

8.1 For IHL Compliance

If “appropriate human judgement and control” is satisfied by *ex ante* parametrisation, then a state deploying an AWS that selects and engages targets without real-time individual human involvement can formally claim compliance with the Rolling Text while fielding a system that is structurally incapable of the contextual judgements that distinction, proportionality, and precaution require. The accountability gap remains open, and may widen as autonomous systems operate in increasingly complex environments where pre-mission parameters cannot anticipate the full range of contexts the system will encounter. The 2021 UN Panel of Experts report on Libya—which described an incident in which a loitering munition attacked in the absence of a communication link with the operator—illustrates this dynamic: the system was formally within programmed parameters, but the human who set those parameters could not have contextualised the specific engagement decision.⁴⁷

8.2 For the Future of the GGE Process

The 2025 Rolling Text is both an achievement and a ceiling. A binding instrument on the terms of the Rolling Text—if one were ever adopted—would be the maximum achievable within the consensus space that includes the major military powers. But it would also be an instrument that those powers could comply with while continuing to develop and deploy systems that challenge IHL at the operational level.

An additional structural problem for any future governance instrument is the fragmentation of regulatory authority over the relevant technologies. As Clapp (2025) documents, civilian drone systems in the EU are subject to comprehensive regulatory frameworks, while military drone use falls under international law exclusively, with the CCW/GGE as

⁴⁷United Nations Security Council (2021). *Final Report of the Panel of Experts on Libya*. S/2021/229. New York: UN, pp. 17–18. The passage describes “a lethal autonomous weapons system” that “had been programmed to attack targets without requiring data connectivity between the operator and the munition” and operated accordingly. The legal implications are analysed by Schmitt and Thurnher (2013) and remain contested.

the primary normative forum.⁴⁸ This fragmentation has two implications for any future LAWS instrument. First, the commercial sUAS/FPV domain—where the Rolling Text’s operative provisions are least developed and where strategic dynamics are evolving most rapidly—falls between the civilian regulatory frameworks (which cover the platforms but not their weaponisation) and the GGE process (which has focused on high-end state-developed systems). Second, the opacity of LAWS programming that Horowitz (2019) identifies as the core verification problem for arms control is compounded by the dual-use nature of the underlying technologies: machine-learning models developed for civilian targeting applications are not distinguishable, at the hardware level, from those deployed in weapons systems, making any instrument that relies on hardware-observable compliance indicators structurally inadequate.

A further illustration of this fragmentation emerged in February 2026, when Anthropic publicly refused to enable two categories of use in its contracts with the US Department of War: mass domestic surveillance and fully autonomous weapons. The company’s statement explicitly distinguished “partially autonomous weapons, like those used today in Ukraine”—which it described as “vital to the defence of democracy”—from “fully autonomous weapons” that “take humans out of the loop entirely” (Amodei 2026).⁴⁹ This distinction maps directly onto the MOTL/HOTL boundary that the Rolling Text fails to codify. The significance is structural: a private vendor has enforced, through contractual refusal, a threshold of human oversight that the CCW/GGE process has spent a decade failing to define. Market mechanisms are producing *de facto* normative constraints in the absence of binding law—but those constraints are unilateral, non-transparent, and reversible.

The TPNW precedent suggests that this may be the eventual trajectory: a treaty signed by the humanitarian coalition that establishes a stigma around a category of systems without constraining the actors that actually deploy them. Unlike nuclear weapons, the relevant technologies are dual-use, commercially available, and proliferating below the threshold of state procurement—which makes the governance challenge qualitatively more difficult.

⁴⁸Clapp (2025), *op. cit.*, pp. 9–11. The Briefing notes that ‘drone regulation remains fragmented: civilian drones are subject to comprehensive EU rules, while military drone use falls under international law’. It further identifies the dual-use problem as particularly acute: the EU AI Act (2024), the most comprehensive AI governance instrument adopted by any jurisdiction, explicitly excludes military uses from its scope, creating a gap between civilian AI governance and military AI governance that no existing instrument bridges.

⁴⁹Amodei, Dario. 2026. “Statement from Dario Amodei on our discussions with the Department of War.” Anthropic, 26 February. Available at: <https://www.anthropic.com/news/statement-department-of-war>.

8.3 For Research and Monitoring

The corpus analysis methodology developed here can be extended to future negotiating cycles, permitting real-time detection of normative drift as new negotiating sessions produce new documents. This has practical utility for civil society monitoring and for legal scholars assessing the evolution of *opinio juris* in this domain. The availability of the replication dataset on Zenodo makes this extension straightforward.

9 Conclusion

This paper has argued that the terminological shift from “meaningful human control” to “appropriate human judgement and control” in the CCW/GGE process is a documentable normative erosion—driven by the structural dominance of states with operational interests in autonomous engagement, and producing a standard that formal compliance can be claimed while the accountability gap that has animated the debate since Phase 2 remains unaddressed.

The argument rests on two evidentiary pillars. First, a quantitative analysis of over 300 negotiating documents traces the frequency and distributional dynamics of key terms across three phases of the debate (2017–2025), documenting the crossover between MHC and “human judgement” in formal GGE outputs while showing that the regulate majority in the wider RCW corpus never converged on the weaker standard. Second, a systematic analysis of eight key state actors and their strategic motivations identifies the structural reasons why the cautious bloc’s preferences prevailed—military comparative advantage (US, Israel, UK), geopolitical identity (Russia), and programme investment in autonomous systems across the regulate centre (France, Germany, and Italy).

The paper has analysed the discourse, not the compliance. Whether systems currently deployed by the United States, Israel, or non-state actors using AI-enabled commercial drones actually satisfy even the weaker “human judgement” standard is an empirical question that requires operational case studies beyond the scope of this analysis. That this standard is being enforced—where it is being enforced at all—by unilateral decisions of commercial AI vendors rather than by international law confirms, rather than alleviates, the accountability gap this paper has documented. That is the research agenda the findings point towards: from the text of negotiations to the practice of deployment. The distance between those two is where the real accountability of international humanitarian law will be tested.

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